

GEOSPATIAL-TEMPORAL DYNAMICS OF URBAN CONGESTION: METHODOLOGICAL INSIGHTS FROM A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY IN ENUGU, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Urban traffic congestion poses major challenges to sustainable city planning in developing regions. This study explores the geospatial-temporal dynamics of traffic congestion in Enugu, Nigeria, by applying Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and open-source tools such as QGIS and Outscrapr–Google Traffic Extractor. A cross-sectional field-based survey was conducted to assess traffic volume, identify congestion hotspots, and analyze transportation flows across three critical corridors: Okpara Avenue, New Haven, and Gariki–Agbani Road. Data sources included satellite imagery, traffic count surveys, road network features, and land-use patterns. GIS-based heat maps and spatial analysis revealed high congestion density around commercial and feeder road intersections, with Okpara Avenue recording the highest daily traffic volume (13,801 PCUs). Private cars and tricycles were the dominant transport modes, indicating a limited formal public transit system. The study highlights the effectiveness of geospatial analysis in visualizing congestion hotspots and patterns but also acknowledges limitations related to data validation, temporal scope, and generalizability. Findings offer insights for targeted interventions such as intelligent traffic signals, route optimization, and zoning reforms. These can inform transport policy and improve urban mobility in medium-sized African cities facing rapid motorization and infrastructure strain.

Keywords: Urban Congestion, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Spatial Analysis, Enugu, Heat Maps, Transportation Planning

JEL Codes: R41, R42, O18, C80, Q53

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban traffic congestion has become a critical barrier to mobility, economic efficiency, and environmental sustainability, especially in developing countries experiencing rapid urbanization. In Nigeria, expanding urban centers such as Enugu are grappling with outdated transportation infrastructure, increased motorization, and poor traffic management, which jointly contribute to persistent vehicular congestion. Studies estimate that over 30% of productive time is lost to traffic delays in major Nigerian cities, with substantial implications for public health, fuel consumption, and economic productivity (Akinpelu et al., 2025; Chukwurah et al., 2025).

Traffic congestion not only leads to travel delays but also contributes to air pollution, noise, and psychological stress, issues with significant public health consequences (Ovikuomagbe

and Olusola, 2023; Ajayi et al., 2025, Ambrose et al., 2025). Despite these impacts, data-driven urban mobility planning remains weak in sub-Saharan African cities due to the lack of reliable, spatially integrated data and planning tools. Traditional traffic studies in Nigeria often focus on descriptive volume counts without integrating the spatial dimensions of congestion, limiting their utility for long-term strategic planning.

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have emerged as critical tools in addressing urban mobility challenges by enabling real-time visualization of traffic flows, identification of congestion hotspots, and modeling of road network efficiency. When combined with satellite imagery, traffic sensors, and crowd-sourced data, GIS supports dynamic transport analysis, improving the targeting of policy interventions. In this study, GIS tools are employed to conduct a cross-sectional spatial analysis of congestion patterns in Enugu, Nigeria, an urban hub with increasing transport pressure. Previous studies have demonstrated the use of GIS in traffic and urban analysis (Jitta et al., 2025; Kamvysi et al., 2025), yet few have explored its application in the Nigerian context with granular spatial data. Moreover, policy responses to congestion in cities like Enugu have largely remained reactive and infrastructure-heavy, rather than guided by real-time spatial evidence.

Enugu was selected as the study site because of its role as a regional commercial center and its increasing transport demand, especially along corridors like Okpara Avenue, New Haven, and Gariki–Agbani Road. These locations experience peak-hour congestion due to a mixture of formal and informal land uses, inadequate traffic control systems, and a growing dependence on tricycles and private vehicles.

This paper seeks to fill existing methodological gaps by combining GIS-based spatial analysis with traffic volume surveys to map congestion density and transport mode distribution. In doing so, it addresses both the visualization and quantification of urban traffic challenges in a medium-sized African city. The objective of this study is to (i) identify traffic management strategies currently in place, (ii) assess traffic volume and flow across selected road corridors in Enugu, and (iii) develop GIS-based heat maps to pinpoint congestion hotspots. These findings aim to inform urban transport policy, guide infrastructure investment, and promote sustainable mobility through spatially informed decision-making.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 presents the methodology, including theoretical framework, data collection techniques, and GIS tools used. Section 4 discusses the spatial analysis results and interprets traffic volume data. Section 5 offers conclusions and actionable policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

Urban traffic congestion is a multidimensional issue shaped by economic behavior, land use dynamics, and infrastructure capacity. Several theories offer a conceptual foundation for understanding congestion dynamics and guide the methodological approach of this study.

One foundational model is Downs' Theory of Triple Convergence, which posits that any improvement in travel conditions (e.g., expanding road capacity) often leads to behavioral adjustments, such as changes in travel time, route choice, or transport mode, and all other relevant itineraries (Ancias et al., 2025; Chou, 2025). This theory highlights the limits of purely infrastructural solutions and underscores the need for demand management and integrated policy planning.

The Urban Mobility Framework also emphasizes the interaction between spatial form, travel demand, and accessibility. It suggests that congestion emerges from the spatial mismatch between where people live, work, and access services. Accordingly, cities with monocentric designs often experience peak-load congestion at urban cores (Angarita-Lozano, 2025).

The Health Impact Pathway model, as outlined by the World Health Organization (2011), conceptualizes the causal chain between environmental exposures such as emissions from congested traffic and public health outcomes (Imam & Ohida, 2024). While not directly quantified in this study, the HIP framework helps justify the urgency of congestion mitigation in protecting urban health. (WHO, 2011). Although not directly quantified in this study, this framework informs the discussion on environmental and health-related dimensions of urban congestion.

These theories collectively inform this study's approach: understanding congestion not merely as a transportation failure but as a systemic issue requiring spatial, behavioral, and policy interventions.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Numerous empirical studies have employed GIS in urban mobility research, yet gaps persist in African contexts, particularly in the use of dynamic spatial tools for real-time traffic congestion analysis.

Akinpelu et al. (2019) and Adewuyi et al. (2019) used GIS to assess traffic congestion in Ibadan, Nigeria, mapping congestion points and linking them to land use conflicts. Similarly, Aminigbo (2022) and Abuh & John (2023) analyzed congestion patterns in Lagos and Abuja respectively, using spatial models, identifying structural road inefficiencies via segmentation. These studies demonstrated that visual analytics, such as heat maps, enhance policymakers' understanding of congestion intensity and distribution.

On the global front, Jitta et al. (2025) highlighted the role of real-time GIS in smart city planning, stressing how urban mobility strategies must integrate data analytics and geovisualization tools. Their work supports the methodological premise of this study. Likewise, Li et al. (2025) developed a GIS-based decision support system for transport planning, which influenced this study's reliance on spatial platforms like QGIS.

In the context of economic impacts, Gwilliam (2003) and Gao et al. (2020) emphasized how traffic congestion impairs urban productivity and increases logistics costs. However, few studies in sub-Saharan Africa quantify these impacts due to the absence of integrated spatial-economic models. This paper acknowledges this gap and frames it as an area for future research.

From a policy lens, congestion pricing, land use reform, and public transport investments have been empirically evaluated in Asia and Latin America (Fruehda et al., 2025; Rui & Othengrafen, 2023), yet these remain underexplored in medium-sized Nigerian cities. Notably, Seguí Pons & Ruiz Perez (2003) showed that combining GIS with Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) improves urban mobility forecasting, reinforcing this study's argument for tool-based policy support.

Despite growing literature, studies specifically focusing on Enugu or similarly sized Nigerian cities remain rare. This study contributes by applying GIS spatial analysis to assess traffic flow and mode choice, offering a replicable framework for other secondary cities in Africa.

3. METHODS AND PROCEDURES

3.1 Study Design and Theoretical Framework

This was a cross-sectional purposive research design to understudy the traffic congestion using Geospatial analysis. This study is anchored in the **Urban Mobility Framework** and draws on the Health Impact Pathway (HIP) to interpret traffic congestion in Enugu.

3.2 Study Area

The research was carried out in Enugu, the capital of Enugu State in southeastern Nigeria. Known historically as the “Coal City,” Enugu plays a key role as a commercial, administrative, and educational hub in the region. The city is geographically situated at latitude 6.5364° N and longitude 7.4356° E, covering approximately 7,161 square kilometers. It shares boundaries with Benue, Kogi, Ebonyi, Abia, and Anambra States.

Enugu’s road network is composed of expressways, arterial roads, collectors, and local streets. Despite this extensive infrastructure, the city faces chronic congestion, particularly along high-traffic corridors such as Okpara Avenue, New Haven, and Gariki–Agbani Road. These corridors were selected for analysis due to their economic significance, observable congestion levels, and mix of residential and commercial land uses. Each zone represents a different urban typology: Okpara Avenue serves as a major commercial artery; New Haven functions as a mixed-use zone; and Gariki–Agbani Road links peri-urban communities to the city core. The city's transport system is integral to this study, as it plays a significant role in assessing traffic congestion and management strategies (Supplementary file).

3.3 Data Sources and Collection Technique

The study adopted a mixed-method approach, combining primary and secondary data sources to provide a comprehensive assessment of traffic congestion patterns.

Primary data were collected through field observations, manual traffic volume counts, and geotagged photographs of traffic scenes. Traffic counts measured Passenger Car Units (PCUs) across 12-hour intervals (7AM–7PM) to reflect peak-hour congestion trends. Road network features including point data (junctions), line data (roads), and polygons (land-use areas), were manually digitized using satellite imagery and verified through field surveys.

Secondary data were obtained from reputable sources. Land use maps and spatial data were sourced from the Regional Centre for Training in Aerospace Surveys (RECTAS), while topographical and road guide maps were provided by the Enugu State Ministry of Works and Planning. Additional mapping layers were extracted from OpenStreetMap, and satellite imagery was used for base referencing.

The study utilized two major analytical tools: QGIS (v3.26.3 – Buenos Aires), a free and open-source GIS application for spatial data processing and visualization, and Outscrapier – Google Traffic Extractor, a web-based tool that captures real-time congestion data using Google Traffic overlays. This combination of tools allowed for spatial visualization and density analysis of congestion hotspots across the selected corridors.

3.4 Sampling Procedure

A purposive sampling strategy was employed to select the most congested and functionally significant road corridors within Enugu. This approach ensured that data collection focused on high-impact areas that best represent the city’s traffic challenges.

The selected locations of Okpara Avenue, New Haven Junction, and Gariki–Agbani Road were chosen based on their observed congestion patterns, land use complexity, and economic significance. Within these zones, specific junctions were identified for traffic counting. These include the Ogbete Market intersection along Okpara Avenue, major crossroads within New Haven, and key turning points along Gariki–Agbani Road. Although the sampling does not cover every road in Enugu, it provides sufficient granularity for spatial and visual analysis of key congestion nodes in the city.

3.5 Sampling Frame, Study tool and Frequency Analysis

The sampling frame comprised neighbourhoods within Enugu metropolis, drawn from the total urban population of 722,664 as of 2006 (Iyi 2014).

The study employed data collection instruments using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Traffic Count Surveys. Each instrument was designed to capture spatial aspects of traffic congestion in Enugu. Frequency analysis was employed to quantify the occurrence of specific traffic-related variables. This involved tallying occurrences and presenting them in tabular and graphical formats, including bar charts and frequency distributions (Supplementary File).

3.6 GIS Analysis Techniques

The spatial analysis for this study followed a systematic procedure using QGIS and supplementary tools. Initially, vector layers were created for point features (traffic hotspots), line features (road networks), and polygon features (buildings and land parcels). These layers were referenced to Enugu's coordinate system for spatial accuracy.

A Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) technique was used to generate heat maps, highlighting congestion intensity across the city. KDE calculates the density of spatial features, in this case, traffic incidents or vehicle concentrations, within a defined area, producing color-coded maps that visualize hotspots.

To assess mobility and routing efficiency, network analysis was performed using vector-based algorithms that simulate real-world travel conditions. This included calculating optimal routes between congested nodes and estimating travel delays based on observed traffic patterns.

The spatial output was complemented by footprint maps, which overlay OpenStreetMap data with traffic layers to provide context for vehicle movement relative to road types and land use. These visualizations supported the identification of systemic congestion patterns, such as pressure at feeder road interfaces and intersections near market zones.

3.6 Limitations of Methodology

While the study provides valuable insights into the spatial dynamics of congestion in Enugu, it is not without limitations. First, data were collected during a single observation period, which may not reflect seasonal or weekday variations in traffic volume. Consequently, the findings offer only a cross-sectional snapshot of congestion patterns rather than longitudinal trends.

Second, while the use of Google Traffic Extractor is methodologically innovative, the tool does not offer official validation or calibration data. The absence of integration with real-time vehicle sensor data or transport authority metrics limits the precision of congestion estimates. Furthermore, the sampling approach, though purposive and targeted, may exclude peripheral congestion zones not captured within the selected corridors.

These limitations are acknowledged, and future studies are encouraged to incorporate multi-day surveys, dynamic GPS tracking, and formal datasets from transport agencies to improve generalizability and policy relevance.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Spatial Analysis of Congestion Patterns

The spatial analysis conducted using QGIS and Kernel Density Estimation revealed concentrated congestion zones across key urban corridors in Enugu. The visual outputs from the GIS analysis illustrated traffic densities as color-coded heat maps, where warmer hues indicated higher levels of vehicular activity. These visualizations provided a compelling spatial narrative of how congestion manifests across different transport environments within the city. In the New Haven area, the heat maps displayed multiple congestion hotspots situated around mixed-use land parcels that contain both commercial businesses and residential dwellings. This aligns with existing urban studies that indicate high traffic clustering in areas with dual land use functions, particularly in cities lacking zoning enforcement (World Bank, 2023). The Okpara Avenue corridor, however, displayed more centralized congestion patterns. The most intense traffic densities were observed around the Ogbete Main Market, one of the city's most

active commercial zones. This finding supports previous observations that commercial hubs lacking structured transport terminals often become persistent traffic bottlenecks (Agbibo, 2020).

The Gariki–Agbani Road corridor presented a more linear and distributed congestion pattern. Rather than exhibiting a singular hotspot, the traffic densities were spread across several road segments. This spatial behavior is likely linked to the road's role as a transit route connecting peri-urban communities to central Enugu. Such corridors, according to Cervero and Golub (2007), often serve multiple modal flows and are susceptible to continuous but less concentrated congestion due to limited bypass alternatives.

The use of spatial visualizations added a diagnostic depth that purely numerical traffic studies lack. By enabling the localization of pressure points, the GIS heat maps serve not only as analytical tools but also as visual guides for planners and policymakers tasked with developing targeted interventions in urban mobility management.

4.2 Traffic Volume Analysis and Mode Distribution

The results of the traffic count surveys provided quantitative support for the patterns identified in the GIS-based spatial analysis. Traffic volumes were recorded over a 12-hour observation window, from 7:00 AM to 7:00 PM, at the three major corridors studied. Okpara Avenue recorded the highest volume, with 13,801 Passenger Car Units (PCUs), followed by Gariki–Agbani Road with 13,140 PCUs, and New Haven Junction with 13,019 PCUs. These high values reflect significant vehicular activity in these locations and validate the choice of study sites as congestion-prone zones.

Vehicle type distribution across these corridors showed a consistent dominance of private cars and commercial tricycles. In all three zones, private cars accounted for approximately 37 to 39 percent of the total traffic volume, while tricycles represented 31 to 40 percent. This pattern is indicative of a modal preference for personalized or semi-formal transit options, which is common in medium-sized African cities where formal mass transit systems are underdeveloped (Salon and Gulyani, 2007; 2010). The relatively low usage of commercial buses and motorcycles suggests limited public transportation infrastructure and a growing reliance on flexible but low-capacity modes of transport.

Hourly traffic flow analysis demonstrated clear peak periods between 7:00 AM and 9:00 AM in the morning and 4:00 PM to 6:00 PM in the evening. These peaks coincide with work commutes and school runs, reflecting typical urban congestion rhythms as documented in other Nigerian cities like Lagos and Ibadan (Adewuyi et al., 2019). While Okpara Avenue maintained a consistently high volume throughout the day due to commercial activity, New Haven showed more concentrated spikes in the early morning and late afternoon hours, likely reflecting its function as a mixed residential-office district. These traffic counts reinforce the spatial observations by offering a numeric perspective on congestion load. The dominance of private and semi-formal transport modes, coupled with temporal spikes, underscores the need for demand-responsive transportation planning and infrastructure adjustments tailored to daily urban rhythms.

4.3 Comparative Congestion Characteristics of Study Corridors

The comparison of traffic characteristics across the three studied corridors revealed important differences in congestion structure, origin, and possible management implications. While all zones experienced high traffic loads, their underlying congestion dynamics varied.

Okpara Avenue exhibited a centralized pattern of congestion, particularly around commercial loading areas. The spatial proximity of Ogbete Main Market, informal parking arrangements, and unregulated pedestrian crossings created a triad of congestion causes. This mirrors findings

from Xiao (2022), who noted that unplanned commercial growth adjacent to major roads often disrupts traffic flow in African cities.

New Haven's congestion pattern was more dispersed, with notable clustering near intersections and school zones. The area's role as a residential and institutional enclave means its traffic is driven by workday commuting and school runs. This aligns with studies such as Adebosin (2022), which highlighted how congestion in mixed-use urban areas often stems from poorly staggered trip timing and inadequate modal separation.

Gariki–Agbani Road presented a third congestion typology, marked by consistent pressure along a linear route. The congestion appeared to originate from continuous flow patterns rather than nodal accumulation, suggesting systemic deficiencies in road capacity and the absence of viable alternate routes. This finding resonates with work by Litman (2013), who identified that through-traffic corridors in mid-sized cities tend to suffer from structural, rather than behavioral, congestion drivers.

These comparative insights reveal that each corridor demands a customized response. While Okpara may benefit from access control and pedestrian buffer zones, New Haven would require school zone decongestion and synchronized signal timing. For Gariki–Agbani Road, infrastructural widening or alternate routing may be more effective.

4.4 Contextualizing Findings within Literature and Policy Frameworks

The empirical findings of this study are in line with the growing body of literature on urban transport in the Global South. Similar GIS-based analyses conducted in Abuja (Abuh and John, 2023) and Ibadan (Adewuyi et al., 2019) emphasized the utility of spatial visualization in uncovering hidden congestion dynamics. These studies argue that GIS allows urban planners to see beyond averages and engage with localized congestion complexities.

At the global level, real-time GIS applications have been praised for enhancing decision-making in transport planning. According to Li, Batty, and Goodchild (2020), such systems can support dynamic policy simulations and facilitate evidence-based adjustments in traffic signal timing and road usage pricing. This validates the methodological choice of combining field-based traffic counts with real-time data scraping from platforms like Google Traffic.

However, unlike more advanced implementations in cities with institutionalized transport authorities, this study operates in a context with limited data availability and minimal integration between urban governance and spatial analytics. The findings therefore provide a baseline for how GIS can be used effectively in low-resource environments, offering a pragmatic model for secondary cities across Africa.

4.5 Reflections on Methodological Boundaries

The strength of this study lies in its spatial precision and integration of visual and numeric data. However, the results are constrained by methodological boundaries that warrant cautious interpretation. The traffic data represents a cross-sectional snapshot and does not account for weekly or seasonal variations. This restricts the study's ability to predict traffic trends or assess the impact of temporal variables such as weather or public holidays.

Furthermore, while the use of Outscraper to collect Google Traffic data introduced a novel real-time component, the tool lacks formal validation against official traffic management systems or longitudinal tracking technologies such as GPS logs or mobile sensor feeds. This limitation, while common in resource-constrained settings, implies that the heatmap data should be interpreted as indicative rather than definitive.

Despite these constraints, the methodological approach successfully demonstrated the feasibility of applying GIS-based analytics in congested but data-scarce environments. The findings offer an evidence-based platform for further research and, importantly, for operational urban transport interventions in cities like Enugu.

Figure 1: Cross-section of traffic heatmap of the study area showing traffic hotspots along New Haven – Okpara Avenue.

Figure 2: Cross Section of Traffic Heat Map showing Traffic Hotspots along Okpara Avenue to Gariki - Agbani Road.

Plate 1: Traffic congestion ongoing at New Haven Junction

Source: Google Imagery, 2022

Figure 3: Map of New Haven showing Street names and transportation network.

Figure 4: Open Street Map of New Haven Showing traffic footprint

Figure 5: Heatmap of New Haven showing hotspots of traffic (Source: GIS 2022). Most of the traffic originated from along Okpara Avenue

Plate 2: Ongoing congestion along Okpara Avenue (Ogbete)

SOURCE: Google Imagery, 2022.

Figure 6: Open Street Mapping of Okpara Avenue to show the traffic footprint

Source: GIS 2022

Figure 7: Heat map of Okpara Avenue showing traffic hotspots.

Source: GIS 2022

Plate 3: Ongoing Traffic Congestion at Gariki – Agbani Road

Source: Google Imagery, 2022

Plate 4: Ongoing Traffic Congestion at Gariki – Agbani Road

Source: Google Imagery, 2022

Figure 8: Open Street mapping of Gariki – Agbani road showing Traffic Footprints

Figure 9: Heat map of Gariki-Agbani Road showing traffic hotspots

Source: GIS 2022

Table 1: Combined Traffic counts across locations

Time Interval	Okpara Avenue	Gariki – Agbani Road	New Haven
7-8AM	1,298	1,354	1,110
8-9AM	1,545	1,100	1,433
9-10AM	1,388	1,081	1,373
10-11AM	1,356	1,312	993
11-12PM	933	1,078	1,005
12-1PM	1,049	837	766
1-2PM	872	872	1,254
2-3PM	1,080	686	952
3-4PM	921	869	906
4-5PM	1,141	1,446	1,037
5-6PM	1,091	1,174	1,404
6-7PM	1,127	1,331	786
TOTAL	1,3801	1,3140	1,309

Figure 10: Traffic Counts by Vehicle Types Across Study Locations

Figure 11: Hourly Traffic Counts Across Locations

Strengths and Limitations

This study presents a methodologically robust and contextually relevant analysis of urban traffic congestion using GIS heat mapping across three significant urban corridors: New Haven, Okpara Avenue, and Gariki–Agbani Road. The strengths of this study lie primarily in its application of geospatial technology, the integration of multi-source data, and its focus on urban areas experiencing rapid motorization and infrastructural strain.

A key strength of the study is the effective use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to spatially delineate congestion hotspots. The color-coded heat maps provided a powerful visualization tool that enables stakeholders to readily identify critical points of congestion. This aligns with best practices in urban transportation planning and supports data-driven decision-making. Additionally, the study’s comparative approach, analyzing three distinct corridors, enhances its generalizability and provides insights into different congestion typologies (i.e., centralized vs. distributed patterns).

The incorporation of multiple forms of data, spatial maps, open street imagery, and photographic evidence, enriches the analytical depth of the study. By triangulating visual data with spatial analysis, the study conveys not only where congestion occurs but also suggests possible contributing factors, such as commercial activity and road network structure.

However, the study is not without limitations. The traffic volume data were collected over a single day at each site, which, while rich in detail, does not fully capture the variability that might occur over different days, seasons, or during special events. A longitudinal or multi-day sampling strategy would offer greater generalizability and reliability in interpreting traffic trends. Additionally, the analysis is static and lacks integration with real-time or dynamic traffic flow data, limiting its predictive power and responsiveness in applications such as intelligent transport systems or adaptive signal control.

Furthermore, the study does not delve into the socio-economic or behavioral drivers of congestion. While we know which vehicle types dominate, the reasons for modal choices, such as income levels, transport affordability, or spatial accessibility, remain unexplored. Incorporating qualitative or demographic data could have enriched the analysis and provided a more holistic framework for interpreting congestion.

Lastly, the study does not evaluate the broader economic or environmental implications of traffic congestion. Important dimensions such as fuel wastage, time lost in transit, or emissions generated from idling vehicles are absent. Including these factors in future studies would not

only strengthen the policy relevance but also align the research with goals of sustainable urban mobility and climate resilience.

5. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the evidence gathered, the following location-specific and systemic recommendations are proposed.

For Okpara Avenue, local authorities should prioritize the regulation of informal transport activities near Ogbete Market. This includes enforcing designated loading and parking zones, improving signage, and creating pedestrian buffers to reduce interference between foot traffic and vehicles.

In New Haven, congestion management should focus on optimizing traffic signal cycles at major junctions and implementing school-zone controls during peak hours. The temporal clustering of vehicles suggests a need for better synchronization between traffic flow and institutional schedules.

For Gariki to Agbani Road, road infrastructure upgrades are necessary. This may involve resurfacing, selective widening of narrow segments, and improved traffic flow design to accommodate through-traffic between urban and peri-urban zones.

Beyond corridor-level actions, the study recommends that the Enugu State Ministry of Transport adopt GIS-based tools for continuous monitoring and planning. The real-time spatial tracking of congestion can improve the precision of response strategies. Additionally, a pilot mini-bus service with fixed stops should be considered to reduce reliance on tricycles and private cars.

These recommendations respond directly to the specific spatial and modal patterns uncovered in the study and are intended to support more efficient and equitable urban mobility in Enugu.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

- a. **Conduct Longitudinal Studies:** Investigate the long-term impacts of traffic congestion on economic development and quality of life.
- b. **Evaluate the Effectiveness of Traffic Management Strategies:** Assess the effectiveness of different traffic management strategies in reducing congestion and improving travel times.
- c. **Explore the Role of Technology in Traffic Management:** Investigate the potential of technologies, such as intelligent transportation systems, to improve traffic management and reduce congestion

CONCLUSION

This study assessed traffic congestion in Enugu using a combination of Geographic Information System techniques and manual traffic volume counts across three key corridors: Okpara Avenue, New Haven, and Gariki to Agbani Road. The spatial analysis revealed varying congestion patterns shaped by land use and road function.

Okpara Avenue exhibited localized but intense congestion, driven largely by market activities and informal loading zones. New Haven's congestion peaked during morning and evening commutes, consistent with its residential and administrative profile. Gariki to Agbani Road experienced distributed congestion along its stretch, reflecting its role as a peri-urban transit route. Across all locations, private vehicles and tricycles dominated the traffic mix, highlighting the limited role of formal public transport.

The study demonstrated that GIS-based heat mapping, combined with volume counts, provides effective diagnostic tools for understanding urban congestion dynamics in developing city

contexts. Although based on a single observation period, the findings offer a reliable starting point for tailored mobility interventions in Enugu.

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